

Characterisation of Interfaces in Micro- and Nano-Composites

T. J. Young^{1*}, M. Monclus¹, W. R. Broughton¹, S. L. Ogin² and P. A. Smith²
¹National Physical Laboratory, Hampton Road, Teddington, TW11 0LW, UK.

²The University of Surrey, Guildford, GU2 7XH, UK.

* Tim.young@npl.co.uk

SUMMARY

This paper details a micro- and nano- scale quality control test for polymeric composite interfaces independent of reinforcement type and geometry. Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), in Force Volume mode, has been investigated as a method of measuring the elastic modulus around the composite interface to characterise variations in mechanical properties and to identify the interfacial quality.

Keywords: Atomic Force Microscopy, Force Volume, Elastic Modulus, Composite, Interface

INTRODUCTION

The ability to predict, accurately, the engineering properties and performance of a composite structure using numerical modelling is critical to the design of any high technology product. Extensive research has been carried out over the years to improve these models although complications arise as assumptions, such as perfect bonding, are often made concerning the interface between the reinforcement and matrix. Due to the limitations of the existing models, laboratory specific samples (e.g. microdroplet test) or large scale mechanical tests (e.g. interlaminar shear) tend to be used to assess the quality of the interface and suitability for purpose. Improvements to composite predictive models are made difficult by the ambiguity of the various measurement methods available and a lack of consensus in the interpretation of data [1].

The quality of the interface is often controlled by using coupling agents (sizing), such as aminosilane for fibre-reinforced plastics, which improve the chemical compatibility between the matrix and reinforcement. Depending on its chemistry, weight percent and method of application, the coupling agent may be a single molecular layer (aiding adhesion) or a separate (or diffused) third phase between the reinforcement and matrix [2]. Various studies have demonstrated the existence of an interphase region, defined as a distinct phase of different properties to those of the reinforcement and matrix or as a region of gradual change in properties/chemistry across the interface [2-5]. In published literature, there is a variation in the terminology used to denote this region, which is called the interphase, third-phase or transition region. For the purpose of consistency, the term interphase will be used here. Two techniques used for the characterisation of the interphase region are nanoindentation and AFM indentation. Both techniques involve pressing a sharp tip (typically less than 150 nm radius) with a characterised geometry, into the surface of the sample whilst monitoring the load and

displacement. Calculation of the surface hardness or elastic modulus is carried out using calibrated tip parameters and models such as that proposed by Oliver and Pharr [6]. Nanoindentation has been used to probe cross sections of fibre-reinforced plastics and to determine the mechanical properties of the interphase which tend to show either a step [2-4] or a gradient [5] as represented schematically in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the two main types of detected interphase, with associated mechanical property variation from the reinforcement to the matrix.

Proper analysis of experimental indentation data requires understanding of the calibrated tip parameters and the nature of the tip-surface contact, which depends greatly on the surface roughness and topography. Accurate assessment of the interphase region requires knowledge of the exact location of the indentation as well as reliable mechanical property measurements. Gao and Mader [7] have studied the effect of indentation area on the detected interphase region for a fibre-reinforced system. It was indicated that there are two possible types of interphase, Type I and Type II, created by the test technique rather than an actual material property, both of which would lead to a higher measured hardness or elastic modulus. Type I behaviour is associated with partial contact with the reinforcement, while Type II arises as a result of a restriction of any plastic zone development around the indentation. It was also suggested that the Type II interphase will extend to approximately 2-3 times the contact radius [7]. Demonstration of the validity of nanoindentation to measure an interphase region, larger than a Type I or Type II interphase, has been published by promoting diffusion of the coupling agent up to 6 μm into the matrix of a phenolic composite by water aging [2].

The advantage of AFM indentation, over conventional nanoindentation, is that the tip can be made smaller and can be controlled with higher accuracy in terms of positioning and minimum applied load. VanLandingham et al [4] have studied the interphase by measuring stiffness from AFM indentations with high spatial resolution (by using a small indenter tip), reducing the possibility of the indenter measuring a composite property. In order to verify the presence and the potential for detection of any interphase by AFM indentation, a thick interphase region was created by coating a copper wire before embedding it within an epoxy-matrix. The measured interphase region (due to the presence of the coating) was approximately 7 μm from the fibre, including a short region of 200 nm where the fibre was proposed to have influenced the indentation response, thereby producing apparently stiffer results [4].

From the evidence of interphase regions, detected by a number of researchers [2-6], there should be a detectable interphase region surrounding many sized or coated reinforcements. What is yet to be established conclusively, is whether or not the detected interphase in each case is caused by the experiment itself, the chemical composition or the mechanical properties of the material. The work carried out by VanLandingham et al [4] shows that it is possible to detect an interphase region, created by a thick coating, using the AFM stiffness measurements. When the interphase region is of unknown dimensions, the indentation measurement must have the highest possible resolution in order to detect the property changes. The AFM acquisition system should deal effectively with the increasing resolution required for mapping, either by increasing the number of indentations or packing the same number of indentations closer together.

In the present work, a range of techniques have been explored for the analysis of AFM indentation data, from relative stiffness mapping [4], to calculation of the elastic modulus directly [9] or by comparison with reference samples [8]. Due to the difficulty of calibrating the AFM tip and cantilever parameters accurately, a variation of the reference sample method [8] was employed to produce maps of the reduced elastic modulus over the interface and highlight any interphase region of different mechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

A variety of materials with different interfacial treatments have been selected in order to assess both the suitability of AFM indentation for detecting the interphase and its existence in terms of a region with thermo-mechanically different properties. The surface preparation method used for the samples was a modified version of the mechanical polishing method employed by Khanna et al [10] with additional ultrasonic bath treatment. The materials and industrial suppliers are as follows:

- Two continuous unidirectional glass fibre-reinforced vinylester pultruded rods, one sample with poor interfacial bonding and the other with good interfacial bonding, supplied by Exel Composites UK Ltd;
- Three glass flake-reinforced polypropylene composite specimens with varying degrees and type of sizing applied to the glass flakes before processing, supplied by NGF Europe Ltd;
- A set of reference samples with modulus values certified by conventional indentation including fused silica, a polymeric photo-stress coating (denoted PS-1) and an ABS-PMMA compression moulded polymer sample.

Due to the number of indentations required to map an area, an algorithm was designed to convert the force-displacement curves and run the required calibration and elastic modulus calculations for multiple indentation curves. Once the AFM tip and cantilever were selected, the following procedure was used.

1. Indentation on the hard reference sample was carried out to establish the cantilever deflection response for a zero depth (i.e. non-penetrating) indentation. The indentation depth due to penetration can then be measured on subsequent samples by subtraction of the cantilever deflection response at each force point (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Indentation force curves before and after correction for various samples and the calibration force curve calculated from indentation on tungsten carbide. Indents were performed using a diamond tip cube corner indenter with a nominal cantilever stiffness of 276 Nm^{-1} .

2. Reference samples were used to establish best fit tip parameters required to calculate the reduced elastic modulus for the “unknown” test sample in step 3. Depending on the tip shape and depth of indentation, one of two models was used, a Hertzian model [11] for spherical tip approximations or an Oliver and Pharr model [6].

- a. For the Hertzian model [11], the unknown tip parameter is the radius, R , calculated from equation 1, using the certified reduced elastic modulus, E_r , for the reference sample. In these equations, α is the contact stiffness calculated from a best fit of the indentation only curve (equation 2), F is the force at indentation depth, h , and $n = 1.5$ for a spherical tip.

$$R = \left(\frac{3\alpha}{4E_r} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

$$F = \alpha h^n \quad (2)$$

- b. For the Oliver and Pharr model [6], the unknown tip function, β , was calculated from the indentation contact depth, h_c . In these expressions, A is the area of indentation, S is the stiffness taken from a best fit of the last 30 % of the approach curve, h_{max} is the maximum indentation depth and $\kappa = 0.72$ for a conical profile and $\kappa = 1$ for a flat punch profile.

$$\beta = \frac{A}{h_c^2} \quad (3)$$

$$h_c = h_{max} - \kappa \frac{F}{S} \quad (4)$$

$$A = \left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \frac{S}{E_r} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

3. The reduced elastic modulus can then be calculated for each indentation on the “unknown” test sample using either equation 6 for the Hertzian model or equation 7 for the Oliver and Pharr model.

$$E_r = \frac{3\alpha}{4\sqrt{R}} \quad (6)$$

$$E_r = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \frac{S}{\sqrt{A}} \quad (7)$$

4. The tip parameters calculated in step 2 were then validated by indentation on reference samples and the tip imaged in the Scanning Electron Microscope

RESULTS

The proposed algorithm method was validated using a range of samples shown in Table 1. Reasonable agreement was obtained with supplier quoted values and continuous stiffness measurements. The AFM tip shape was measured using the SEM to ensure that the tip parameters calculated from reference samples were realistic and that tip geometries remained stable during testing.

Table 1: Experimentally obtained elastic modulus values for various indentation methods and tip geometries for the reference samples and case study materials. The Poisson’s ratio, ν , is given for all calculated values.

Test method	Tip geometry	Tip radius	Elastic Modulus (GPa)					
			Fused Silica	PS1	ABS	PMMA	Vinylester	C glass
	(nm)	(nm)	$\nu = 0.17$	$\nu = 0.4$	$\nu = 0.35$	$\nu = 0.35$	$\nu = 0.35$	$\nu = 0.17$
Unknown method, quoted by supplier				2.5	2.5	3.5	3.8	unquoted
Continuous Stiffness	Berkovich diamond	<200 nm	70 (quasistatic indentation)	2.3-2.5	2.35 ± 0.05	4.8 ± 0.05	3.5 ± 0.1	62.5 ± 1.7
AFM indentation	Cube Corner Diamond	< 50 nm			2.36 ± 0.89	6.33 ± 0.66	4.95 ± 0.39	60.89 ± 4.99

The results obtained in table 1 indicate that AFM indentation is not as accurate as continuous stiffness measurements, although reasonable agreement is made with the predicted values. AFM indentation has a lower contact depth than nanoindentation and so the errors associated with establishing the contact area are higher, although the higher positioning accuracy and lateral resolution capabilities offset this disadvantage. It is clear that AFM indentation is capable of measuring the differences in the elastic modulus between samples and that any interphase present should be detected.

AFM indentations were performed on various reference samples before and after testing on the glass flake specimens in order to establish how constant the tip shape parameters were before and after indentation mapping. For each system, a topographic image was taken prior to indentation to look for a clean surface and avoid topographical features and select a suitable interface. Indentations for all glass flake specimens were performed using a 200 Nm⁻¹ nominal stiffness cantilever, with a 7°

cone angle and a sub 20 nm radius single crystal diamond AFM tip indenter. Reduced elastic modulus values, E_r , were calculated using the Hertzian model. Figure 3 shows two sets of indentations made over the interface of a glass flake-reinforced polypropylene sample with no applied aminosilane.

Figure 3: Two sets of AFM indentations across unsized glass flake-reinforced polypropylene interfaces. Each set of measurements corresponds to 32×4 indentations with indents spaced 312.5 nm apart.

The indentation map, for each of the two unsized samples, demonstrated the capability of AFM to measure the reduced elastic modulus on both the reinforcement and the matrix. It was not expected to measure any true interphase region as no sizing was present. The results show a significant data scatter on the glass flakes that may be caused by changes in tip between indents or the effect of surface roughness. Where indentation occurred at the edge of the flake, it is possible that the scatter in the measured elastic modulus is due to compliance of the substrate underneath the flake. Glass flake-reinforced polypropylene samples with 0.05 wt% and 0.28 wt% aminosilane sizing were prepared and a series of indents were mapped over the interface for a number of flakes. It was expected that the 0.05 wt% sized system would show a 1 μm interphase and the 0.28 wt% sized system would show an extended gradient beyond 1 μm .

a) Figure 4a: Single line of indents on the 0.05 wt% sized glass flake system indicating a 1 μm interphase region. Figure 4b: Four lines of indentations on the 0.05 wt% sized glass flake system indicating no detectable interphase region.

Figure 4a shows a single line of indentations indicating a step interphase of approximately 1 μm in length. The SEM image of the tip size indicates that the step interphase is at least three times the contact radius, although this step is only represented by a single line of indentations and unrepeated in any further lines. It is a

challenge to establish whether or not the presence of an apparent interphase is due to the aminosilane sizing polypropylene interaction or a product of the test, especially where the interphase is only represented by a fraction of the indentations measured. Figure 4b shows four lines of indentations over the interphase, none of which indicate the presence of any interphase region. Good practice requires that individual presented sets of data should be representative of the whole. Over 100 lines of indentations in total have been carried out for the 0.05 wt% aminosilane sized specimen and, as only one shows the distinct interphase, it cannot be taken as representative of the whole. The spread of data and challenge of maintaining a constant contact area function on surfaces with high surface roughness means that large numbers of indentations are required to show subtle changes in surface properties. The interphase region was expected to be larger for the 0.28 wt% aminosilane sized glass flake-reinforced specimen and a high-resolution indentation map is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Reduced elastic modulus values mapped over the interface of the 0.28 wt% aminosilane sized system from 128 x 32 indentations.

The results, shown in Figure 3 to Figure 6, do not indicate any clear interphase region although the data demonstrates the ability to detect the difference between the reduced elastic modulus of polypropylene and glass. Two continuous unidirectional glass fibre-reinforced vinylester pultruded rods, one sample with poor interfacial bonding and one sample with good interfacial bonding were examined using force modulation AFM and transmission electron microscopy to establish the presence of any interphase region. In Force Modulation AFM, the amplitude of an oscillating cantilever is recorded as it scans over a surface. The oscillation amplitude is larger for soft areas, as the tip indents more into the surface, than for hard areas. From the AFM and TEM results the pultruded rod, with poor interfacial bonding, was considered to have an interphase region of $\approx 100\text{-}350$ nm surrounding the fibre-reinforcement. Figure 7 shows a Force Modulation image indicating a dispersed interphase region schematically described by Hodzic et al [2] and a TEM image showing a cross section of the interface showing a possible interphase region of different density to either the bulk matrix or the fibre. The challenge for force modulation AFM is discerning whether or not the changes in amplitude are due to adhesion forces, surface stiffness, change in the tip shape during scanning, or a change in the tip-surface contact area (contact at an edge due to surface profile).

a) b)
 Figure 7a: Force Modulation image of a glass fibre-reinforced vinylester with poor interfacial bonding showing different amplitude for the bulk matrix, interphase and fibre. 7b: TEM image of the same sample a glass fibre-reinforced vinylester with poor interfacial bonding showing interphase region of different structure to the matrix and reinforcement.

The interphase region may exhibit different morphological properties, resulting in possible changes in the tip-surface contact area, due to differences in surface roughness or extreme profiles. It is also possible that the interphase exhibits different chemical composition to the surrounding matrix, resulting in a variation of adhesion forces, due to a greater affinity between the tip and the interphase surface chemistry. It is possible to explain the regions of lower amplitude on the fibre, as regions of polymer contamination on the surface, although it is difficult to explain regions of higher relative amplitude on the polymer unless the interphase has been dispersed into the matrix. AFM indentation should indicate whether or not the Force Modulation AFM and TEM images, in Figure 7, indicate an interphase with varying stiffness and/or thermo-mechanical properties. Figure 8 shows the results of a 16 x 16 AFM indentation map, taken on the sample with poor interfacial bonding shown in Figure 7. The indentations were taken using a cube corner diamond indenter with a tip radius of less than 40 nm and reduced elastic modulus values calculated using the Oliver and Pharr model. Indents were spaced with a separation of 312 nm to prevent overlap.

Figure 8: AFM indentation results for the glass fibre-reinforced vinylester-matrix with poor interfacial bonding. The circle indicates a single indentation that of approximately 14 GPa.

At 1.75 μm only a single indentation gives any indication of a region of different stiffness (approximately 14 GPa) although it is not clear, from AFM non-contact

images post indentation, whether or not this particular indent infringed on the fibre itself. To increase the number of datapoints possible to measure at the same length scale a sapphire cantilever of 200 Nm^{-1} nominal stiffness, with a single crystal diamond tip with a sub 20 nm radius and a 7° cone angle was used to repeat the measurement with 128×64 datapoints. This leads to an indentation separation of just over 39 nm requiring extremely low forces to prevent indentations from overlapping or any developed plastic zones from infringing. A modulus image is shown in Figure 9 with three lines of indentations plotted separately in Figure 9b for clarity.

a) Figure 9a: AFM indentation results for the glass fibre-reinforced vinylester with poor interfacial bonding. 96×50 lines displayed over $4 \mu\text{m} \times 1.95 \mu\text{m}$. Figure 9b: Three lines of AFM indentations taken from figure 9a illustrating the gradient interphase and interfacial disbond.

The measured elastic modulus values on the vinylester matrix are between 8 GPa and 14 GPa , which is at least 3 times the expected value. This may be due to the close packing of indentations, indicating that the plastic deformation zone surrounding the indentations did overlap. The plastic deformation zone could also be larger than predicted due to a change in tip shape after indentation on the reference samples. It is worth noting that after the 50th line (6400 indentations) the tip lost contact with the surface due to a large change in tip shape and no further data were recorded. SEM images and recalibration of the tip parameters, on reference samples, indicate that the tip fractured and required resharpener using a focused ion beam. Despite the high recorded values for the matrix, and loss of contact after the 50th line, it would still be possible to detect any changes in the recorded mechanical properties at the interface. Three single lines of indentations are shown in Figure 9b to indicate that a number of features of the interface were detected. In the immediate proximity to the interface, at approximately $4.2 \mu\text{m}$ in Figure 9b, there is a region of negligible stiffness which could indicate a region of degraded material or an interfacial failure. Figure 9 shows a gradient in the detected elastic modulus properties (marked in Figure 9b) for 500 nm between the reinforcement and the interfacial disbond that may indicate the presence of aminosilane on the surface of the fibre. Assessment of whether the gradient is purely a product of the aminosilane is not possible due to the known change in tip shape after indentation on the reference samples and a fracture after the 50th line of indents. It is likely that the interphase is due to partial contact with the edge of the fibre, although supporting evidence given by Force Modulation AFM and TEM indicate the presence of an interphase region with similar dimensions. Work is

currently underway to establish a method of detecting uneven loading, beneath the indenter tip, in order to distinguish between measurements that are a product of the interphase and those that are due to artefacts such as tip slip, partial contact with the fibre (Type I interphase) or restriction of the plastic zone (Type II interphase).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The suitability and practicality of an AFM indentation test method in order to map the elastic modulus around an interface has been evaluated. An algorithm for analysing multiple force-displacement curves has been designed and mapping of the elastic modulus for a range of samples has been achieved. Where the tip geometry remains stable before and after indentation mapping, the measured elastic modulus is in good agreement with certified values. Indentations across the interface for the glass flake-reinforced polypropylene composites indicate no consistently detectable interphase with dissimilar elastic modulus to the bulk matrix. The results from TEM and Force Modulation AFM indicate an interphase for the glass fibre-reinforced vinyl ester composites and the high-resolution indentation map gave evidence of an interphase with a elastic modulus along its length. The AFM indentation test method also showed the ability to detect an interfacial disbond. Work is currently underway to establish a method of identifying indentations, over the interface, that are due to artefacts thus eliminating the main source of errors when characterising the interphase region.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This paper was supported by the National Physical Laboratory as part of a Department of Innovation Universities and Skills (DIUS) funded project. TJY would like to acknowledge support from the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) in the form of an Engineering Doctorate programme. The authors would like to thank Chris Stevens and David Mason (NGF Europe Ltd), John Hartley (Excel Composites Ltd) and colleagues David Cox, Nigel Jennett and Charles Clifford for their technical support and advice.

REFERENCES

- [1] W R Broughton, L E Crocker and M J Loderio: Characterising micro and nanoscale interfaces in advanced composites: A review: *NPL Report* DEPC-MPR 055: 2006
- [2] A Hodizc, Z H Stachurski and J K Kim, "Nano-indentation of polymer-glass interfaces Part I. Experimental and mechanical analysis", *Polymer* 41 (2000) 6895-6905
- [3] A Hodizic, J K Kim and Z H Stachurski, "Nano-indentation and nano-scratch of polymer/glass interfaces. II: model of interphases in water aged composite materials", *Polymer* 42 (2001) 5701-5710
- [4] M R VanLandingham, R R Dagastine, R F Eduljee, R L McCullough and J W Gillespie JR, "Characterization of nanoscale property variations in polymer composite systems: 1. Experimental results" *Composites: Part A*, 30 (1999) 75-83
- [5] J-K Kim, M-L Sham and J Wu, "Nanoscale characterisation of interphase in silane treated glass fibre composites", *Composites: Part A* 32 (2001) 607-618

- [6] W C Oliver and G M Pharr, "An improved technique for determining hardness and elastic modulus using load and displacement sensing indentation experiments", *Journal of Materials Research*, Vol 7, Number 6 (1992) 1564-1583
- [7] S-L Gao and E Mader, "Characterisation of interphase nanoscale property variations in glass fibre reinforced polypropylene and epoxy resin composites", *Composites: Part A* 33 (2002) 559-576
- [8] C A Clifford and M P Seah, "Quantification issues in the identification of nanoscale regions of homopolymers using modulus measurement via AFM nanoindentation", *Applied Surface Science*, Vol 252 (2005) 1915-1933.
- [9] B Tang, A H W Ngan and J B Pethica, "A method to quantitatively measure the elastic modulus of materials in nanometer scale using atomic force microscopy", *Nanotechnology*, Vol 19 (2008) 495713
- [10] S Khanna, R Winter, P Ranganathan, SB Yedla, M Kalukanimuttam and K Paruchuri. "Sample Preparation techniques for nano-mechanical characterization of glass fibre reinforced polyester matrix composites", *Composites Part A*, Vol 34, (2003)
- [11] D C Lin, E K Dimitriadis and F Horkay, "Robust Strategies for Automated AFM Force Curve Analysis-I. Non-adhesive Indentation of Soft Inhomogeneous Materials", *Journal of Biomechanical Engineering*, Vol. 129, Number 3 (2007) 430 – 440